

Modern Tools Used When Working on Adjective Words in Primary Grades

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Abstract:

This article describes the process of working on quality vocabulary in elementary grades and the tools used during this period. This article is relevant as it provides theoretical information about the method, technology and didactic games, as well as the technique of practical application. The tools are covered within the framework of four stages of primary classes.

Keywords: system, term, stage, technology, program, lexical meaning, opportunity, situation, preparation, connection.

INTRODUCTION

Unlike all word groups, the system of learning the adjective word group envisages consistently enriching and complicating the material from the lexical and grammatical side. Since the process of working on word groups in elementary school students is a complex process, it is carried out in stages. The process of studying adjectives is in the same form, as follows: (according to the requirements of DTS)

METHODOLOGY AND DISCUSSION

Primary school students observe the lexical meaning of the adjective in the first and second grades (that is, they understand the meaning of the words belonging to the adjective group, they can ask questions);

In the third grade, the adjective is studied as a word group, that is, the grammatical features characteristic of it are gradually revealed;

In the fourth stage of primary classes, the information learned within this vocabulary is repeated. Certain spell-related rules specific to quality levels are taught. In this process, the term “quality

levels” is not used, the characteristics specific to the levels are not revealed, only the orthographic rules specific to the increasing level (words written with an increase in sound, for example, green, blue-blue) are explained. . An understanding is given that the indicated words should be written with a dash.

In the process of obtaining the information presented above on the basis of experiments, and after the process, in the native language and reading classes, the students’ speech is enriched with new adjectives, the meaning of the adjectives they already know is clarified, i.e. is consciously explained to the reader.

In primary grades, in general, at any stage, the process of learning an adjective word group is based on the linguistic features of this word group. Adjectives indicate the sign of an object. Based on this sign, quality is divided into the following groups:

- Adjectives indicating color (color-color adjectives);
- Adjectives indicating the size of the subject (volume, measurement adjectives);
- Taste qualities;
- Characteristic qualities;
- Odor qualities;
- Weighing qualities;
- Time-space qualities (these qualities are determined by time and place).

One of the requirements in the process of learning an adjective word group is to learn it in connection with a noun word group. Therefore, from the first grade, all attention should be paid to connecting adjectives to nouns. The advantage of this method is that the students say the symbol of the object and students develop the skill of linking words together. To clarify, in this process, students learn to make a word combination from nouns and adjectives. But in this period, the term “word group” is not used. As we move to the next stage, the characteristics of this concept become deeper and clearer. Working on two, semantic and grammatical features of the adjective word group requires the following two tools:

- Lexical (morphological);
- Grammatical (syntactic).

The process of quality study is conducted on the basis of the principles of consistency, systematicity and dependence. The principle of consistency is as follows;

First, the teacher introduces students to the basic characteristics of quality. This process covers the first and second stages of primary classes.

The process of giving an understanding of the adjective word group covers the third class;

The fourth stage consists of teaching the correct orthographic spelling of some adjectives in parallel with grammatical features.

Although the initial introduction to quality begins at the first stage, the term “quality” is not used in this chapter. It begins with observation of lexical meaning and questions. The signs of the subject are diverse and describe it by its color, taste, shape, and characteristics. It is clear from this that in order to create an understanding of the adjective phrase in the student, it is necessary to clarify its meanings. One of the ways to effectively carry out this practical process is to use pictures. This method helps to focus the student’s attention, expand the range of imagination, and bring his

abilities parallel to thinking. When the teacher shows the picture, the students say the symbol of the object in it. For example, a book is a big book; like an apple-red apple.

Gradually, students begin to consciously understand the meanings of the adjectives that they have been using in their oral and written speech until today. In order for students to understand more deeply the role and importance of the words they denote in our speech, there are different types of instructions.

Exercises, modern interactive methods and smart technologies should be used.

The role of modern interactive methods and smart technologies in education Currently, education, which is rapidly developing on the basis of foreign experiences, requires high skills from the teacher. Today, the market economy also needs personnel with creative and innovative ideas. The formation of creative thinking and innovative ideas in the mind of the student begins to grow depending on the education and training given from the age of elementary school. The role of modern interactive methods, didactic games and smart technologies is of particular importance in the formation of knowledge in the student with an effective and positive result without much effort. Together with the formation of high knowledge in the student, they encourage them to think, expand the scope of imagination, focus, resourcefulness and interest in the learning process. Forms the skills of conscious understanding, knowledge and skills in young children who have just been disconnected from play activities.

Adjectives are tools specific to the word group

The ideas based on the above scientific experiments can certainly give us the idea that the organization of the lesson process through all interactive methods, modern didactic games and smart technologies will lead to a successful result. But this concept is wrong. After all, not all means can give positive results in the end. That is, the teacher cannot use whatever tool he wants. The tools used (modern interactive method, smart technology and didactic games) have several requirements for high results, which are as follows:

The tool used during the lesson should be suitable for the age of the student. There are certain methods and technologies that are intended only for high school students. A teacher can stay away from such tools or make changes based on his/her abilities;

The selected tools should match the essence of the topic or be multi-functional;

Methods must be specific to the class capability. Implicit in this rule is the notion that there are technologies and tools that may not fit all classroom capabilities.

Through this scientific work, we have researched several modern technologies and tools. We think that these methods and technologies will give good results.

The word under the term “fan” can express two concepts. That is, the interactive method can be used as a didactic game. Guidelines for practical application as a didactic game are described as follows:

This didactic game has just moved away from the game activity has a good effect on students.

It encourages you to think first and then draw a conclusion.

This didactic game requires advance preparation from the teacher, that is, the teacher must have hand-made fans in the process of organizing this didactic game.

The list of words (in mixed form, containing nouns, adjectives, etc.) is read out to the students.

This game can be organized with students of the whole class. The number of students depends on the discretion of the teacher.

The condition is that the student should listen and think about the words that the teacher is reading, and if the adjective belongs to the group of words, he should move the fan in his hand.

In this didactic game, both mental and physical activity is carried out in the student.

CONCLUSION

The use of modern methods and technologies in the educational process helps to further develop the abilities of a young student. Students develop creative thoughts and ideas through these tools.

List of used literature:

1. “Methodology of mother tongue teaching” Karima Kasimova, Safo Matchonov, Khalida Gulomova, Sharofat Yoldosheva and others. Tashkent – “Nasir” publishing house. 2009
2. The State Education Standard-2017 developed by the Republic Education Center “Technology of educational games”